

Studies in Formation and Properties of Carbon-sulphur Surface Complexes. Part II. Stability of Carbon-sulphur Complexes formed on Charcoal

Balwant Rai Puri, C. M. Jain and Ram Singh Saxra

Carbon-sulphur solid complex, formed on treatment of charcoal with H_2S or CS_2 vapour at the optimum temperature of 600° is highly stable. It decomposes only on high temperature treatment, upto 1200° , in vacuum or in a current of nitrogen when the combined sulphur is liberated mostly as H_2S or CS_2 together with small amounts of sulphur vapour. The heat treatment in a current of hydrogen results in the elimination of the entire amount of sulphur as H_2S . Stability of the complex and desorption of combined sulphur as CS_2 indicates strong valency forces operating in the chemisorption of sulphur by carbon.

As reported earlier¹, a considerable amount of sulphur can be fixed by sugar as well as coconut charcoal on treatment with carbon disulphide or hydrogen sulphide at the optimum temperature of 600° . Similar fixation of sulphur by other types of carbons has also been reported.²⁻³ Very little information is, however, available regarding stability of the complex formed and the manner and form in which it can be desorbed. The present paper describes the results obtained on heating the treated charcoal either in vacuum or in a current of nitrogen or hydrogen at different temperatures.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sugar charcoal⁶ was treated with H_2S or CS_2 at 600° for 8 hr. The treated (sulphurised) material was extracted with CS_2 in a Soxhlet apparatus for a week (10 hr. a day) to get rid of any sticking or physically held sulphur. The material was dried in an air oven at 120° and stored in tightly corked bottles flushed with nitrogen.

The dried material (1 g.) was boiled with 2.5 *N*-NaOH (100 ml) in a 250 ml flask under reflux for 12 hr. On testing the solution was found sulphur free.

The sample (1g.) taken in a platinum boat, was placed in a silica tube (18" $\times$ 3/4") which was heated electrically to a desired temperature upto 1200° , either in vacuum or in a current of nitrogen or hydrogen (at the rate of 2.5 litre/hr). The outgoing gases were passed through a spiral tube to condense sulphur vapour, if any, and then through a series of Erlenmeyer flasks containing standard ($\approx$ 0.1 *N*) iodine solution to remove H_2S . The

1. Puri *et al.*, (communicated).
2. Fischer and Franschke, *Brennst. Chemie*, 1929, 10, 361.
3. Wibaut and Van der Kam, *Proc. K. Akad. Wetensch. Amsterdam*, 1929, 32, 501.
4. Eriksson and Wetterholm, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1947, 1, 889.
5. Lewis and Metaner, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1957, 40, 849.
6. Puri *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 4890.

amount of sulphur was estimated by washing the spiral tube with CS_2 and that of H_2S by noting decrease in the concentration of the iodine solution.

The amount of CS_2 released from the sulphurised charcoal was estimated separately by heating another 1g- portion to the same temperature. The outgoing gas was first allowed to pass through the spiral tube and anhydrous calcium chloride (to condense sulphur vapour and to remove moisture) as before, and then led over activated charcoal (5g.) contained in a small weighed U-tube, cooled in an ice bath. This technique had been checked in control experiments. Incidentally, estimation of CS_2 was not possible when the heat treatment was done in vacuum as the amount adsorbed would volatilise readily. The amount of sulphur retained by the charcoal was estimated by Eschka's method.⁷

DISCUSSION

As the combined sulphur cannot be removed even in traces on prolonged boiling with NaOH (conc.) solution, the carbon-sulphur complex is assumed to be highly stable. Table I shows that the decomposition of the complex, on heating in vacuum, commences only when the temperature is raised to 500° and that the combined sulphur is released more as H_2S , due evidently to combination of the sulphur with residual hydrogen in the charcoal, than as free sulphur. An appreciable amount (about 6%) of the combined sulphur is, however, retained by the charcoal even on outgassing at 1200° .

Another important feature of the data presented in Table I is that the entire amount of sulphur cannot be accounted for as sulphur vapour and H_2S evolved and sulphur retained. The unaccounted sulphur might have been evolved as CS_2 which, however, as already mentioned, could not be determined in this case as outgassing was done in vacuum. But in those cases in which outgassing was done in a current of nitrogen subsequently, it was found that the unaccounted sulphur could be recovered substantially as CS_2 , as will be shown shortly. Undoubtedly, the unaccounted sulphur in this case too must have escaped as CS_2 . If so, it appears that a greater proportion of the sulphur is released as CS_2 , the amount increasing with rise in temperature.

TABLE I

Decomposition of carbon-sulphur complex formed on sugar charcoal (by treatment with H_2S) on heating in vacuum at different temps.

Amount of sulphur fixed = 7.56 m.e./g. or 0.121 g./g.

Evacuation temp.	*Sulphur evolved as		*Sulphur	
	Free sulphur.	H_2S .	Left in the residus.	Unaccounted.
300°	nil	nil	7.56	nil
500°	0.05	0.36	6.01	1.14
700°	0.03	0.43	5.82	1.28
900°	0.08	1.40	3.07	2.91
1200°	0.28	2.04	1.20	4.04

*Expressed in m.e./g.

7. Scott, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", D. Van Nostrand, Co. Inc., N. Y., p. 906, 1938.

The heat treatment in nitrogen is seen to be more effective in decomposing the complex (Table II). This is in keeping with the previous observations that the heat treatment in nitrogen is more effective in eliminating the carbon-oxygen and carbon-hydrogen complexes⁸. The complex formed on treatment with CS_2 is also seen to come off as sulphur, H_2S and CS_2 , indicating that this complex has essentially the same characteristics as that formed by treatment with H_2S .

TABLE II

Decomposition of carbon-sulphur complex formed on sugar charcoal (by treatment with hydrogen sulphide as well as carbon bisulphide) on heating in a current of nitrogen at different temps.

Temp.	Complex formed on treatment with H_2S . (Sulphur fixed=7.56 m.e./g. or 0.121 g./g.)			S left in the the residue	Complex formed on treatment with CS_2 . (Sulphur fixed=12.23 m.e./g. or 0.196 g./g.)			S left in the residue
	Sulphur evolved as				Sulphur evolved as			
	Free S	H_2S	CS_2		Free S	H_2S	CS_2	
400°	nil	0.11	0.39	6.85	nil	0.26	1.62	6.66
500°	nil	0.21	0.62	6.37	nil	1.99	1.97	7.36
700°	0.10	1.50	0.69	4.82	0.01	4.38	1.92	4.76
900°	0.12	2.61	1.01	3.31	0.11	3.96	2.51	4.21
1200°	0.12	3.12	3.04	0.23	0.13	4.70	4.80	0.32

N.B. Amount expressed in m.e./g.

The results obtained on heating in a current of hydrogen are recorded in Table III. It is seen that now the entire amount of sulphur gets desorbed as hydrogen sulphide. The magnitude of the decomposition of the complex is seen to increase with rise in temperature, approaching about 50 per cent in 600-650° temperature range and completion in 900-1200° temperature range.

TABLE III

Decomposition of carbon-sulphur complex formed on sugar charcoal (by treatment with hydrogen sulphide as well as carbonbisulphide on heating in a current of hydrogen at different temps.

Temp.	Complex formed on treatment with H_2S . (Sulphur fixed=7.56 m.e./g. or 0.121 g./g.)		Complex formed on treatment with CS_2 . (Sulphur fixed=12.23 m.e./g. or 0.196 g./g.)	
	*Sulphur		*Sulphur	
	Evolved as H_2S .	Left in the residue	Evolved as H_2S .	Left in the residue
900°	0.40	7.20	0.80	11.53
500°	2.32	5.35	1.63	10.92
700°	4.40	3.10	6.90	5.12
900°	7.00	0.51	11.70	0.60
1100°	7.56	nil	12.41	nil

*Expressed in m.e./g

The fixation of sulphur by carbon on treatment with H_2S and its desorption on treatment with hydrogen evolving H_2S establish the reversibility of the surface reaction:

This again brings out the analogy of this reaction with the water-gas reaction as has been pointed out earlier¹.

The results presented here indicate not only great stability of the carbon-sulphur complex but also reveal, probably for the first time, that a considerable proportion of sulphur is released as CS_2 on desorption. This indicates the existence of strong valency forces binding sulphur to surface carbon atoms such that sulphur, when desorbed, can tear off some of the underlying carbon atoms as well. This brings out close analogy of this complex with carbon-oxygen solid complex which is known to come off as oxides of carbon².

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
PANJAB UNIVERSITY,
CHANDIGARH-3.

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